

A Source of Bibliotherapy: Happiness and Spirituality in Tolstoy's Story Called "Ilyas"

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Abstract

While happiness has been a fundamental human desire throughout history, the contemporary pursuit of happiness, shaped by consumerism, materialism, and digital media, can paradoxically undermine happiness. Individuals who fail to achieve happiness or experience dissatisfaction often seek support through counseling and therapeutic interventions. The primary aim of this study is to examine Tolstoy's short story Ilyas, which represents today's pursuit of happiness and emphasises true happiness, using the document analysis method. The story clearly presents a comparative perspective on Ilyas and his wife's outlook on happiness before old age, during their period of wealth, and after they lost all their possessions. The research uses content analysis to report the story's search for happiness, its consequences leading to unhappiness, and the location of true happiness. Excerpts from the story are included. In this context, Ilyas and his wife's pursuit of happiness reflects today's materialistic and possession-oriented pursuits. The resulting excessive work and concern for increasing and protecting their possessions lead to numerous unhappiness-causing consequences. Findings show that the pursuit of materialistic and work-centered happiness leads to unhappiness through lack of quality time with loved ones, damaged relationships, fear, anxiety, fatigue, and disorganization. In the final chapters of the story, Ilyas and his wife realize true happiness, finding it particularly in their satisfying close relationship, the prevailing peace of mind over anxiety, their greater avoidance of sin compared to their previous lives, their dedication to their inner world, and their religious and spiritual experiences. In addition, within the scope of the research objective, the opinions of psychological counselors were obtained. The psychological counselors think that the story titled Ilyas can be used as a bibliotherapy resource in relation to happiness. They also think that clients who read the story may realize that true happiness is fundamentally nourished not by material elements, but by spiritual and relational sources, processes of awareness and meaning-making, and the ability to manage life in a healthy manner. The study concludes that the story may serve as a bibliotherapy resource in psychological and spiritual counseling and be applied in empirical research on happiness within religious psychology, spiritual counseling, and psychological counseling.

Keywords: Spiritual-Psychological Counselling; Bibliotherapy; Story; Happiness

Introduction

Psychological and spiritual counseling fields utilize numerous theories and methods in the process of providing services. One method used in the counseling process is bibliotherapy. Bibliotherapy is a method that aims to help clients understand themselves, identify their problems, and identify potential solutions by using books related to the client's needs and problems (Öner, 2007).

Stories are one of the resources used in bibliotherapy. The awareness-raising and healing aspects of stories can be utilized in the counseling process (Öner, 2007). Stories are an effective way to teach values, behavioral standards, and life lessons. Throughout history, teachers such as Jesus, Buddha, Sufis, and Zen Buddhists have used stories, and stories are also featured as a primary form of communication in the Bible. Fairy tales and stories have become a universal means of transmitting cultural values and the content of good living between generations (Burns, 2021). The client connects the story to their own life and talks about their conflicts and desires. This is because stories enhance comprehension and understanding. Stories encourage the client to consider their problems from new perspectives and offer real and positive solutions. These solutions offered by stories serve as a tool for discussing the client's problems (Peseschkian, 2019).

This study aims to analyze the content related to happiness in Tolstoy's short story "Ilyas" as a source of bibliotherapy. Happiness has been valued by people throughout history and remains a significant goal desired today. The factors that positively and negatively impact happiness and its consequences are the subject of extensive research. Despite this, many individuals today who cannot find satisfactory answers to their search for happiness receive psychological support. The purpose of this study is to examine Tolstoy's short story "Ilyas," which reflects the modern quest for happiness and ultimately emphasizes true happiness, and to evaluate it from a bibliotherapy perspective, in order to provide support to individuals seeking counseling services in the context of happiness.

Literature Background

Happiness

Happiness (subjective well-being) is the experience of positive emotions in various areas of one's life, a low level of negative emotions, and overall satisfaction with one's life (Biswas-Diener vd., 2004; Diener, 1984; Diener vd., 1999, 2003; Diener & Diener, 1996). Happiness has many positive effects on an individual's health, relationships, and quality of life vardır (Biswas-Diener vd., 2004; Lyubomirsky, 2019; Lyubomirsky vd., 2005). In this direction, happiness is highly valued in every society. Despite this, many people may experience inadequacy and dissatisfaction in their pursuit of happiness and have difficulty achieving true happiness. Therefore, why are people still unable to achieve true happiness (Schmid, 2020; Wong, 2010)?

Today, people often seek happiness in material things, and materialism stands out as a belief system that ties happiness to possessions and goods. The assumption that owning luxury items brings greater happiness has become widespread (Belk, 2001). Consequently, extrinsic values such as wealth, fame, and image have gained importance, especially in America and increasingly in other societies. Despite the fact that these values are known to harm happiness, advertisements and social media constantly glorify them (Ryan & Deci, 2017). In such an environment, people strive to achieve happiness through extrinsic and symbolic values (such as respect, prestige, status, power, and protection against humiliation) to avoid being left behind (Bauman, 2011). However, these material symbols or values can be misleading, because quality of life depends more on how we feel about ourselves and our experiences than on what we possess and what others think of us (Csikszentmihalyi, 2021). Therefore, rather than increasing material resources and trying to influence others through them, improving the quality of experiences and making daily life more harmonious and fulfilling offers a more meaningful path to achieving true happiness. Therefore, instead of symbolic goals, a more direct path that will provide real fulfillment can be chosen (Csikszentmihalyi, 2021).

Many wealthy and successful people, who seek happiness through material success and, in turn, own luxurious homes and expensive cars, are unable to find peace and happiness and therefore seek therapy (Csikszentmihalyi, 2021). Therefore, individuals seeking happiness strive to understand what happiness is, how it is felt, and the factors that shape it, and to make this feeling

permanent in their lives (Çivitçi, 2012). In this context, it is believed that Tolstoy's story "Ilyas" can be a useful bibliotherapy resource to raise awareness for clients seeking happiness in psychological and spiritual counseling processes. This is because Tolstoy's stories, with their universal themes and human values, support individual and spiritual development (Maylıba, 2016). Tolstoy was not only a literary genius but also a versatile writer noted for his intellectual depth and moral sensitivity. His works went beyond the era in which he lived and served as both a pedagogical and moral guide (Maylıba, 2016).

Tolstoy's Story Called Ilyas

The influence of Tolstoy's works is felt even today, demonstrating his powerful character. He implemented the values he espoused in his works in his own life, deeply impacting people (Yaşar & Ceylan, 2024). Tolstoy was not only a literary genius but also a versatile writer noted for his intellectual depth and moral sensitivity. His works transcended his time, serving as both pedagogical and moral guides. Tolstoy argued that for the meaning of life, one must aim for goodness in one's conscience. In his works, he explored themes such as sincerity, human relationships, the purpose of creation, the meaning of life, prayer, and the dangers of greed (Maylıba, 2016). Regarding his educational role, he undertook initiatives in public education, and his works are considered treasures, particularly in terms of character and value education (Maylıba, 2016; Pala, 2021).

Tolstoy's interest in Eastern cultures, particularly Turkish and Arabic thought, began with his study of Arabic-Turkish literature at Kazan University and deepened with his dialogues with Turkish captives and his curiosity about the moral fabric of the Turkish people. During Tolstoy's lifetime, Turkish literature was virtually unknown in Russia. Similarly, there were insufficient and high-quality translations from Turkish into Western European languages. Despite this, Tolstoy was interested in Turkish folk culture, recognized elements such as fairy tales, legends, traditions, and proverbs, and strived to introduce them to Russian readers. To this end, he included content reflecting folk wisdom in Russian-language reading books and other works. This interaction with Turkish literature paved the way for his works to resonate widely in Turkey; they were translated and appreciated by many Turkish writers (Şifman, 2021).

Tolstoy's story "Ilyas," discussed in this study, was the first Russian literary work translated into Turkish by Lebedeva. The reason for the story's translation into Turkish is its close resemblance to Turkish culture (Olca, 2017). Furthermore, this work demonstrates Tolstoy's sympathy for Islam (Jafarov vd., 2024). This work has generated considerable interest, particularly in Muslim Eastern countries and Turkey. The search for a moral ideal and the fundamental principles of universal morality can be seen in this story (Мухиддинов & Хусенова, 2020, s. 302). Indeed, according to Tolstoy, true human happiness lies not in material success, but in moral self-improvement and the attainment of inner maturity (Pala, 2021). The story "Ilyas," which parallels this idea of Tolstoy's, depicts the life of an elderly couple who, despite living a life of wealth for many years, have been unable to find happiness, but who find true peace only after losing everything. Ilyas and his wife, Şem-Şemagi, initially grieve over the loss of their wealth; however, over time, they realize that the disorder that comes with wealth and the constant anxiety to protect their possessions are actually making them unhappy. Later, they begin to live a simple, orderly, and peaceful life, expressing their true happiness. In other words, when the opportunities life offers are gone, they realize their true values and find peace in a simple life (Taşkın, 2021). The pursuit of happiness centred on wealth depicted in the story is a materialistic quest for happiness that is prominent today, portrayed in films and television series, promoted in advertisements, and propagated on social media. Therefore, where do people today look for happiness, and where do they seek it? Do the things they find provide true long-term happiness? Or does their search yield more distress, fatigue, emptiness, and meaninglessness than happiness? The story can encourage readers to reflect on these questions and draw conclusions for their own lives. Therefore, it deserves to be considered as a source of bibliotherapy in counseling environments and as a resource with the potential to be included in the content of values education and psychoeducation programs. In this context, it is thought that the study will contribute to the literature, counselling and guidance practices, educational studies, and readers.

Method

This study employed a qualitative research method. Qualitative research involves a process in which qualitative data collection methods—such as interviews, observation and document analysis—are used to gather non-numerical data (such as words and images) in line with the study's objectives; it involves a holistic examination of events and perceptions within their natural

context (Creswell, 2014; Johnson & Christensen, 2014; Yazıcıoğlu & Erdoğan, 2011). The research method used in this study is document analysis. This method involves systematically examining books, brochures, magazines, newspapers, letters, and similar materials to obtain information relevant to the topic or purpose of the research (Bowen, 2009; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). The analytical process involves identifying, selecting, evaluating, and synthesizing data in documents. This method is an iterative process that involves both superficial and comprehensive examination of the material, and the interpretation and interpretation of the data. Content analysis also reaches categories relevant to the research topic (Bowen, 2009). In this study, the behaviors that do not bring happiness and the elements that do bring true happiness in Tolstoy's story "Ilyas" were examined using content analysis, and the data were presented as themes. In addition, the views of psychological counsellors were sought to evaluate the document analysis within the context of the study. To this end, ethical approval was obtained from the Scientific Research and Ethics Committee of Necmettin Erbakan University (dated 3 April 2026, No. 7). The psychological counsellors' views on the story were analysed using content analysis.

The Document Examined: The translation of the story "Ilyas" into modern Turkish, used as a document in this research, appears at the end of the book "What Does a Man Live On?" published by Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Yayınları (Karaca, 2023; Taşkın, 2021). The book "What Does a Man Live On?", part of the Hasan Âli Yücel Classics Series, consists of 86 pages, while the story "Ilyas" is a short story of six pages. Other stories in the book are "What Does a Man Live On? The Fire That Does Not Quench the Spark Cannot Be Contained, Girls Are Smarter Than Grown-Ups, The Candle, Does a Man Need Much Land?" (Tolstoy, 2017). Koray Karasulu, who translated the book, is a translator who successfully translated the works of prominent figures in Russian literature such as Dostoyevsky, Gorky and Tolstoy into Turkish and won the Ömer Asım Aksoy Translation Award given by the Language Association in 2014 (Taşkın, 2021).

Validity and Reliability: As with other types of research, validity and reliability are crucial issues in studies involving document analysis. To strengthen the weaknesses of document analysis, the documents examined are compared with data obtained from studies using different data collection tools such as observation and interviews. These supporting studies are important in increasing the validity and reliability of the research (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). In this context, to increase the validity and reliability of the research, psychological counselors (n=42) were asked

to evaluate the story from a bibliotherapy perspective. In addition, psychological counselors were asked to examine the story and to indicate what clients who read the story might become aware of in relation to happiness. Accordingly, the findings obtained by the researcher and the opinions of the psychological counselors were presented in the findings section, and similarities among the results were observed.

First and foremost, in document analysis studies, the purpose of selecting the document to be examined is of great importance. The reason for choosing the story titled "Ilyas" is that it emphasizes the concept of true happiness in a way that is relevant to the study's aim, represents the contemporary individual's search for happiness, and reveals that the pursuit of happiness through misguided approaches often leads to various factors that result in unhappiness. Furthermore, the story highlights elements that contribute to true happiness as significant components within the context of happiness. The counselors consulted stated that the understanding of happiness discussed in the first part of the story reflects today's "materialistic" and "possessive" pursuit of happiness. They also suggested that the story could be used as a bibliotherapy tool when working with clients who are searching for happiness.

One reason for choosing the story titled "Ilyas" is that it is a work that has garnered significant attention. The book "What Does Man Live With?", which includes the story "Ilyas," is considered a world classic and is included in the "100 Basic Works" published by the Ministry of National Education to be taught in schools every year between the 2004-2005 and 2017-2018 academic years (Taşkın, 2021). It is noteworthy that the book is among the sixteenth most read books among the 100 basic works by students; it is the third most read with admiration; and it is considered the second most read with curiosity (Okur & Arı, 2014). The story's short, engaging, and engaging structure, its inclusion among the most read works, and its intense emphasis on values further enhance its value (Taşkın, 2021). This also indicates that the story could contribute to educational, counseling, and guidance services in schools. Because the brevity, conciseness, and effectiveness of the work are significant advantages for clients. Especially for clients who don't enjoy reading, the brevity of the story can make it easier for them to accept reading.

Document analysis has some weaknesses. For example, documents may provide incomplete information relevant to the research objective (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). For instance,

the story titled "Ilyas," examined in this study, while not encompassing every element or factor contributing to happiness, has the potential to prompt the client to reflect on true happiness. However, the primary aim of using bibliotherapy is to enable the client to gain insight by addressing such works in the counseling setting. It can be said that the happiness-related content of the story has the potential to contribute to raising awareness and developing new perspectives on happiness in the counseling process. The counselors consulted also stated that the story has the potential to raise awareness about pursuits that do not bring happiness and the elements that provide true happiness. It can be argued that this awareness can also encourage the understanding of different happiness-related elements and concrete life examples that are not directly included in the story.

A second weakness of document analysis is the possibility that the document may be limited to the author's perspective and the message they wish to convey (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). The author highlights the points they observe and want to emphasize from their own point of view. Although this is the case, it can be said that the presented content may open doors to new ideas for the reader. In this context, the quality of the chosen work and the identity of the author are important. Tolstoy is a writer known worldwide for his works, has a wide readership, and is valued from a literary perspective. The chosen work, Ilyas, is compatible with Turkish (Olca, 2017) and Islamic culture (Sebziyeva, 2023) and reflects Tolstoy's sympathy for Islam (Jafarov et al., 2024). The story has also aroused great interest in Muslim Eastern societies and in Turkey (Муриддинов & Хусенова, 2020). Accordingly, it can be said that Tolstoy and his story titled "Ilyas" hold value for Turkish society.

Findings

Themes Related to Happiness in the Story Named 'Ilyas'

This section primarily analyzes Ilyas and his wife's pursuit of happiness that does not bring them happiness, and the negative psychosocial consequences that result from this pursuit and lead them to unhappiness. In addition, the conditions that lead to true happiness at the end of the story are discussed.

Theme 1: Things that don't bring happiness

Table 1 lists the actions and situations in the first section of the story that Ilyas and his wife resorted to in an attempt to find happiness, but which ultimately led to their unhappiness.

Tablo 1. Things done to be happy in the story but did not bring happiness

Theme	Sub-Theme
Things that don't bring happiness	<i>Ambition</i> to accumulate money and possessions
	Abundance, wealth, and <i>increased</i> wealth
	Hard work
	Fame, renown, recognition
	Striving to look good (Efforts to avoid embarrassment)
	Having a wide variety of pursuits

According to Table 1, the ambition to accumulate money and possessions, abundance, increasing wealth and fortune, hard work, fame, reputation, recognition, the effort to look good (the effort to avoid embarrassment), and a wide variety of pursuits emphasized in the story constitute the life cycle and routines of Ilyas and his wife. All of these are orientations and behaviors for happiness, but they are not situations that bring happiness.

Theme 2: Consequences of pursuits that do not bring happiness

Table 2 lists the various situations/consequences that Ilyas and his wife encountered in their search for happiness, which made them unhappy. These consequences clearly illustrate the negative situations that befell the characters in the story and the negative changes in their lives.

Tablo 2. Consequences and explanations of pursuits that do not bring happiness

Theme	Sub-Theme	Explanations
The consequences of pursuits that do not bring happiness	Lack of free time	Ilyas and his wife were constantly working, leaving them unable to create free time in their lives. This prevented them from finding time for relationships (love, affection, and conversation) and spiritual experiences (prayer and spiritual reflection).
	Social appearance anxiety	The constant effort they put into hosting guests and looking good has left them feeling anxious and compelled to maintain their social image.
	Anxiety about protecting	As their wealth increased, Ilyas and his wife became

one's property (from wolves, thieves)	anxious to protect their wealth, which disturbed their peace and caused them to live their lives in constant fear.
Distrust of servants	The distrust they feel towards the servants, the constant anxiety of protecting their property and the loss of trust in their relationship have increased the couple's inner unrest.
Children's negative behavior (spoiled, drinking, disrespecting their father, take liberties)	Wealth and hedonism have encouraged irresponsible behavior and bad habits in their children, which has become a factor that disrupts relationships and peace within the family.
Inner restlessness	Years spent in constant work and worry prevented Ilyas and his wife from finding peace and caused them to live a spiritually unsettled life.
Do not sin	Constant anxiety, stress, and conflicts of interest damaged Ilyas and his wife's religious beliefs and spiritual values, causing them to experience sins such as having bad attitudes towards the servants.
Inability to have spiritual experiences such as prayer	Working constantly has led Ilyas and his wife to drift away from spirituality.
Not being able to think about their souls	In their pursuit of wealth and possessions, they have abandoned their spiritual and spiritual development, which has increased their sense of inner emptiness.
Conflict and quarrel between spouses	Problems related to wealth and fortune have led to frequent conflicts and arguments between spouses, resulting in loss of peace in their marriages.
Loss of sleep	Because of their wealth and worries, Ilyas and his wife's sleep was not regular and they lived such an anxious life that they could not sleep at night.
Discomfort	The stress they experienced physically and mentally disturbed them and negatively affected their quality of life.
Anxiety or worry about the future	The constant fear of losing their wealth and uncertainty about the future caused the couple to be in a constant state of anxiety.

The results in Table 2 reveal how the choices Ilyas and his wife made in their pursuit of happiness negatively impacted them. External goals such as wealth, social status, and the accumulation of possessions created constant anxiety and restlessness in their lives, preventing

them from finding inner peace and spiritual happiness. Lack of free time for religious, spiritual, and human values, social appearance anxiety (striving to appear good to others, fear of disgrace), negative developments within the family, fear of property damage, thoughts of sin, and the negative physical consequences of overwork all undermined the couple's mental and physical health.

Theme 3: Situations that bring happiness

In the second part of Tolstoy's story "Ilyas," Ilyas and his wife discover true happiness after losing all their possessions and undergoing a period of adjustment. During this process, they find inner peace by escaping the anxiety, conflict, and unnecessary burdens of their previous lives. When guests at the house question Ilyas and his wife's new understanding of happiness, they openly express what true happiness is. Table 3 presents these elements of happiness and the transformation experienced by Ilyas and his wife.

Table 3. Things and explanations that true happiness is achieved in the story

Theme	Sub-Theme	Explanations
Situations that bring happiness	Love and closeness	After losing their wealth and property, Ilyas and his wife found inner peace through the love and closeness they felt for each other.
	Conversation	The couple, who used to live a life full of worries and conflicts, now spend time in peaceful conversations with each other.
	The end of conflicts	The couple, who used to fight constantly because of wealth and worries, states that these conflicts have now ended and they live a peaceful life.
	The disappearance of anxieties	Once the wealth was lost, the anxieties disappeared; the stress brought on by wealth, money, and society's expectations gave way to peace.
	Having a certain purpose and order (to fulfill the assigned tasks)	Ilyas and his wife now act with a certain purpose and order in their lives, making their daily lives meaningful by fulfilling the assigned tasks.
	Working with desire	The couple, who used to work out of necessity and anxiety, now work willingly and peacefully, because they are seeking inner peace and meaning.
	Meeting basic needs (clothing, food, shelter)	Ilyas and his wife state that meeting their basic needs, clothing, food and shelter, is now a source of peace and

	that they do not need much property and wealth.
Being able to think about their souls	After distancing themselves from wealth and workload, they have been able to devote more time to spiritual development and inner thoughts.
Pray	During this period, in which they found meaning in their lives, Ilyas and his wife embraced prayer to God as a source of peace.
Having free time	Instead of the stress brought on by wealth and work, having free time now is another factor that brings them inner peace.

Table 3 clearly illustrates the factors that led Ilyas and his wife to achieve true happiness in their lives after abandoning their desire to accumulate wealth and possessions. At the end of the story, elements such as love and closeness, conversation, the end of conflicts, the disappearance of anxieties, having a certain purpose and order (to fulfill the assigned tasks), working with desire, meeting basic needs (clothing, food, shelter), thinking on their souls, praying to God, and having free time are associated with happiness. In other words, human values such as love, closeness, and conversation come to the fore. Freed from their anxieties (damage to their material possessions, distrust of servants, concern for appearance, etc.), the couple achieved inner peace by escaping the restlessness caused by these anxieties. Furthermore, the end of old conflicts related to work and the establishment of order in everything became a new source of happiness for them. Meeting their basic needs, eliminating excessive preoccupations, and creating free time also played important roles in their happiness. Being able to thinking on their lives and souls, praying to God, and thinking about not repeating previous sins provided them with spiritual peace and contributed to their happiness.

The pursuits that do not bring happiness, the situations that cause unhappiness, and the situations in which true happiness is achieved in Tables 1-3 can be clearly seen in the following dialogues in the story:

- I'm telling the truth, I'm not joking: We searched for happiness for half a century, but when we were rich we found nothing; now we have nothing, we live with someone else, but we found such happiness that we don't want anything better.

- *So what is your current happiness like?*

- *Look here: When we were rich, my husband and I didn't have a single hour of peace; we couldn't talk, we couldn't think about our souls, we couldn't even pray. We had so many things to do! Guests would come, and we'd worry about what to serve them, how to entertain them, so they wouldn't criticise us. When the guests left, we had to keep an eye on the servants; their only concern was shirking work and filling their bellies, while ours was protecting our property from them. We were sinning, in other words. We struggled to keep the wolves from attacking the lambs and the thieves from stealing our horses. You'd get into bed, but you couldn't sleep for fear that the sheep would crush the lambs; you couldn't rest easy without getting up in the middle of the night to check on the sheep. Then the anxiety would start again, wondering where to find feed for the winter. As if that weren't enough, my old man and I were always arguing. He'd say it should be done this way, I'd say it should be done that way, and we'd fight and sin again. That's how we lived, amidst all these worries, committing all sorts of sins, never seeing any happiness.*

- *What about now?*

- *Now, when we wake up in the morning, my husband and I talk affectionately and amicably. We have nothing to fight or worry about. Our only job is to serve our master. We work willingly, to the best of our ability, so that our master makes a profit rather than a loss. When we return from work, lunch and dinner are ready; we also have kumis. In winter, we have dung for fuel and coats to keep us warm. We also have time to talk, reflect on our souls, and pray to God. We searched for happiness for fifty years, but only now have we found it.*

An examination of the views of psychological counselors regarding the story

The usability of the story "Ilyas" as a bibliotherapy resource in the context of the search for happiness has been evaluated by psychological counselors working in the field. Four closed-ended and two open-ended questions were posed for this purpose.

Table 4. The suitability of the story titled "Ilyas" as a bibliotherapy guide related to happiness

Closed-ended questions	Yes (n)	No (n)
Do you think the story "Ilyas" could be used as a bibliotherapy resource with clients who are searching for happiness?	40	2
Does the "materialistic" and "possessive" pursuit of happiness, which Ilyas and his wife find truly unhappiness in the first part of the story, represent the pursuit of happiness in our modern world?	41	1

Could clients who read this story gain an awareness of pursuits that don't bring happiness?	39	3
Could clients who read the story gain an awareness, by the end, about what brings true happiness?	40	2

Table 4 shows that the story of Ilyas can be used as a bibliotherapy resource for clients seeking happiness (n=40, 95.2%); it has the potential to raise awareness among individuals about pursuits that do not bring happiness (n=39, 92.9%) and elements that can truly bring happiness (n=40, 95.2%). Furthermore, the "materialistic" and "possessive" pursuit of happiness, which does not truly bring happiness to Ilyas and his wife and is depicted in the first part of the story, is noted as representing the nowadays understanding of happiness (n=41, 97.6%).

In response to the question, "What do you think clients who read the story might recognize regarding the elements that contribute to true happiness?", psychological counselors have presented similar and related views based on story analysis.

Table 5. Contents that clients reading the story may notice for true happiness

Theme	Sub-Theme	Code
Questioning the Perception of Material Happiness	The negative effects of material ambition (stress, anxiety, fear, fatigue, conflict)	23
	Material possessions do not guarantee happiness	12
	Material goals/ambitions leading to the neglect of important things in life	3
	Excessive materialism reduces spiritual and religious orientation	2
Spirituality	The nurturing role of spiritual life	7
	Awareness of inner happiness	4
	Contentment	3
	Tending to Allah	2
	Gratitude	2
The Importance of Relationships	Spending time with loved ones	7
	Conversation (listening, understanding, sharing)	5
	Healthy communication	4
	Love	2
	Spouse support	1
Awareness and the Search for Meaning	The meaning of life	4
	Self-awareness	3

	Orientation toward the inner world	3
	Change of perspective	2
Life management	Simple living	5
	The need to slow down	4
	Calmness	4
	Living in the moment	3
	Quality time	2
	Balanced life	1

According to Table 5, psychological counselors believe that clients who read the story may become aware of many issues related to happiness within the context of the story. In this regard, the findings are grouped under themes such as questioning materialistic conceptions of happiness (f=40), life management (f=19), relational happiness (f=19), spirituality (f=18), and awareness and the search for meaning (f=12).

Psychological counselors believe that clients can question their perception of material happiness by reading the story. In this context, clients can become aware of the negative effects of material ambition, such as stress, anxiety, fear, fatigue, and conflict, and see that material possessions do not guarantee happiness. They can also understand that material goals and ambitions can lead to the neglect of important aspects of life and that excessive materialism can weaken spiritual and religious orientation. For example, according to the participants: Clients may realize that *"while chasing material gain, they are missing out on life, and this rush causes them anxiety and fatigue"* (Participant 8). Similarly, *"Ambition and excessive pursuit of materialism can sometimes unknowingly cause them to miss out on many beautiful things in life"* (Participant 21). They believe they can reach an awareness of *"Losing time for God due to the desire to acquire possessions, and then fighting with those around them over worldly matters"* (Participant 1).

According to psychological counselors, within the context of spirituality, clients reading the story can recognize the nurturing role of spiritual life in terms of happiness, the importance of inner peace, and the value of contentment, tending to Allah, and experiences of gratitude. Clients who read the story may realize that *"what nourishes the human soul is not only material but also spiritual nourishment, and that the focus should be shifted away from materialism."* (Participant 17) *"They may realize that happiness depends more on spiritual richness than material wealth."* (Participant 18).

Under the theme of the importance of relationships, clients may realize the importance of spending time with loved ones, having conversations, healthy communication, love, and spousal support for happiness. According to psychological counselors, clients can recognize relational values such as "*spending time together, being content with little, affection*" (Participant 28); and "*healthy communication, mutual love and respect, etc.*" (Participant 10).

Under the theme of awareness and the search for meaning, clients can understand the importance of meaningful life, self-awareness, and turning inward for happiness, and experience a positive shift in perspective. For example, according to psychological counselors, clients who read the story "*can recognize the things that make life meaningful for them. From an existential perspective, they can express the work and actions that bring them peace and enable them to achieve lasting happiness, not temporary happiness.*" (Participant 35) "*They can grasp the importance of living a more meaningful life spiritually.*" (Participant 4)

Under the theme of life management, clients can realize the importance of simple living, slowing down, calmness, quality time, and balance, rather than a fast-paced and intense life focused on material things. For example, according to psychological counselors, within the context of the story, clients "*can become aware of what they want and don't want. Clients who become self-aware can then organize their environment.*" (Participant 40); "*They can begin to use their time more effectively.*" (Participant 20); "*They can experience the comforting effect of a simpler life with fewer responsibilities, spending time with each other, finding time for prayer, etc., and focusing more on implementing decisions rather than making them.*" (Participant 6).

In summary, while psychological counselors draw attention to the risks of pursuing material happiness, they emphasize that true happiness can arise from a spiritual and inner orientation rather than materialistic ones, and highlight the importance of prioritizing spiritual and human values. In a general summary, the following views of two psychological counselors can be included: Clients reading the story may realize that "*satisfying close relationships are more important, that overwork can harm spiritual values, that overwork and the fear of losing material possessions can make people unhappy, and that they need to allocate time for religious and spiritual life. They may*

realize that human and spiritual things are more important than material life for happiness. They may realize that material possessions and wealth are not a guarantee of happiness." (Participant 2); Similarly, clients may realize that *"spirituality, peace, and shared experiences with one's life partner are more important than material elements for happiness."* (Participant 1).

Result and Discussion

This study examines Tolstoy's story "Ilyas" as a potential bibliotherapy resource for individuals seeking support regarding happiness. The first part of the story paints a general picture of Ilyas and his wife's lifestyle, centered on material success. This lifestyle reflects the accumulation and preservation of their material possessions, a self-presentation based on these possessions (striving for recognition, fame, and good looks), and a sense of worthiness. The consequences experienced by Ilyas and his wife regarding material values (material possessions, money/wealth, fame) demonstrate that external/material success does not bring true happiness; on the contrary, it creates more anxiety, conflict, and unrest (Table 1). In fact, the literature has concluded that giving relatively more importance to materialistic values and goals (wealth, popularity, image) can harm happiness (Kasser vd., 2014; Kasser & Ahuvia, 2002; Kasser & Ryan, 1993). In this context, psychological counselors who have examined the story also think that the materialistic and possession-oriented understanding of happiness described in the first part of the story represents the nowadays understanding of happiness, and that the story can be used within the scope of bibliotherapy with clients who are searching for happiness.

In the later parts of the story, Ilyas and his wife, who lost all their means and possessions for happiness, began working as servants, and experienced a sense of self-awareness in the process, find true happiness in spiritual and human values. The couple's feelings of love and closeness; their free time for themselves and each other, listening to themselves (their souls) and each other, and their conversations; the elimination of conflicts and anxieties that caused unhappiness; their structured and fulfilled duties within the context of their servanthood and their work with passion; their basic needs being met; and their inclusion of religious and spiritual matters such as prayer to God and abstaining from sins stand out as the ingredients that constitute their true happiness (Table 3). Therefore, this story demonstrates that the material prosperity that comes with wealth and status does not guarantee happiness; that true happiness must be based on values such as love, inner peace, meaningful relationships, a simple life, and spirituality. Therefore, Tolstoy's story "Ilyas"

is not only a literary text; it can also be considered a guide to life, a mirror of values, and a tool for spiritual awareness. Because this is one of Tolstoy's aims. In his stories, Tolstoy offers guiding messages and offers guidance for people by offering wisdom from the experiences and wisdom of the elderly (Yaşar & Ceylan, 2024). In the story, Ilyas and his wife, with their old age, experience, and the wisdom they have acquired, encourage the other characters in the story and the readers to reflect on what true happiness is. Therefore, the story titled Ilyas can be used as a bibliotherapy tool in the fields of psychological and spiritual counselling when working with clients seeking happiness; thus, the story can offer various perspectives to discuss with the client and open different doors.

For people to achieve a good life and true happiness, the importance of weakening the orientation or lifestyle toward materialistic values/goals, which are encouraged by consumer culture, and increasing intrinsic values such as contribution to society, close relationships, self-acceptance (personal development), and health is emphasized (Kasser, 2015). In this respect, Ilyas and his wife's materialistic pursuit of happiness can be used as an example of bibliotherapy to raise awareness and weaken materialistic orientation. Furthermore, the second part of the story also draws attention as a source of bibliotherapy for increasing intrinsic and self-transcendent values such as close relationships, an inner orientation, and spiritual experiences, the values through which Ilyas and his wife find happiness. Psychological counselors who examined the story also think that clients who read it may gain awareness about pursuits that do not bring happiness and about what truly leads to happiness..

Psychological counselors who examined the story have put forward views supporting document (story) analysis regarding its potential contributions within the context of bibliotherapy. Psychological counselors believe that clients reading the story can recognize many important points regarding happiness and therefore the story can be used effectively in the counseling process. The most frequently emphasized theme in the participants' statements is the questioning of the equation of materialism with happiness. It has been stated that clients can realize that money, status, and possessions alone do not provide happiness, and that they can understand more deeply that as material gain increases, so do responsibilities, and this can trigger anxiety, stress, and the fear of loss. In this context, it is seen that material ambition can lead to the overlooking of many meaningful values in an individual's life. However, clients can realize that true happiness is not

fundamentally derived from material elements, but from spiritual and relational resources, awareness and meaning-making processes, and the ability to manage life in a healthy way. The findings reveal that the story has a bibliotherapeutic function in developing awareness in individuals and contributing to the restructuring of value orientations.

A review of the literature reveals that many opinions and studies on the relationship between material life and happiness reflect the message the story aims to convey and the views of psychological counselors. The relationship between money and happiness is complex, and research indicates that when money is used appropriately-that is, to support spiritual, cultural, and intellectual values-it contributes to happiness (Leslie, 2009). Although wealthy nations are on average happier than poorer nations, it has been concluded that an increase in wealth does not raise life satisfaction at the same rate, meaning that an increase in material wealth does not always guarantee happiness (Diener & Oishi, 2000). Similarly, it has been concluded that although being wealthy contributes to happiness, it does not guarantee it; how money is used is more important for happiness (Diener *et al.*, 1985). Another study found that individuals who act with integrated motives (such as self-esteem, philanthropy, market value, freedom) in earning money appear happier than individuals who try to earn money with non-integrated motives (such as impulsivity, social comparison, overcoming self-doubt) (Thibault Landry *et al.*, 2016). Based on their research findings, Rath and Harter (2010) offer five key recommendations for increasing the contribution of money to happiness: Learn to be content with your income and aim to be happy with it; adopt a lifestyle in line with your income and do not exceed your means; spend money wisely and save consciously (make short- and long-term plans); direct your spending not only towards material objects but also towards meaningful experiences, as experiences can become lasting and satisfying memories over time; use money not only for your own needs but also in ways that benefit others (Hafferon & Boniwel, 2014).

In modern societies, public policies generally view wealth as the primary source of happiness; however, once basic needs are met, the contribution of income growth to happiness remains limited. While having money contributes to happiness to a certain extent, making money the main goal in life can be detrimental (Biswas-Diener *et al.*, 2004). Although wealth increases happiness up to a certain point, focusing solely on economic growth does not seem sufficient when considered alongside increases in divorce, suicide and crime rates. Furthermore, the constant

pursuit of material gain can make individuals selfish, alienate them and undermine their happiness. Therefore, the purpose of wealth should not be to accumulate more wealth, but to produce a higher level of well-being (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000; Seligman vd., 2009). In today's societies, where basic needs are largely met, the focus of public policy should no longer be solely on economic growth but on elements such as happiness, health, education, and quality of life; the economy should be seen as a means to serve these values (Biswas-Diener vd., 2004).

One of the issues that must be emphasised in order to evaluate true happiness in the context of the story is the meaning of life. As in his story *Ilyas*, Tolstoy highlights the themes of man's search for himself and questioning the meaning of life in his stories (Yaşar & Ceylan, 2024). According to Frankl, the founder of logotherapy, life must be meaningful in order to be happy. Happiness is a by-product of meaning. According to him, some of the things that give meaning to life are, as mentioned in the story, the existence of relationships with other people and with God. Therefore, religion, which is expressed as the ultimate meaning, and the relationships that people establish based on love can add meaning to life (Frankl, 2018b). In the story, material things that cause unhappiness and the excessive focus on them are, as Frankl emphasises, indicators of meaninglessness and consequently unhappiness. Because working excessively for material success is an attempt to fill an existential void or meaninglessness. According to him, money or material success is not insignificant. What is important is that it does not lose its function as a means and is not seen as an ultimate goal (Frankl, 2018a). As seen in the first part of the story, *Ilyas* and his wife's main focus is that material resources, which should be a means, have become an end in themselves and encompass their entire life. Tolstoy approaches the question 'What is the meaning of life?' within a religious and moral framework, and according to him, if life is limited to the material dimension, it becomes meaningless and inconsistent. Only when one views life with a high level of consciousness does life become an expression of a journey towards wisdom, meaning, and purpose (Smanbekova, 2002). The story *Ilyas* also narrates the process by which characters who cannot find the true meaning of life and are unhappy discover true meaning and happiness as a result of the breakdown they experience. The story titled '*Ilyas*' is both a reflection of the author's personal spiritual quest and an internal response to the question 'How should one live?' Tolstoy guides his readers to deeply contemplate the meaning of life, the source of true happiness, the nature of true harmony, and the essence of inner peace. This form of suggestion lends both literary and philosophical depth to the story (Sebziyeva, 2023). Therefore, Tolstoy's aim of encouraging

his readers to reflect can also contribute to clients' lives in terms of questioning, making sense of, and deciding on happiness during counselling sessions.

The story titled Ilyas holds value within the fields of religious education, religious psychology, and spiritual counselling. This is because the story also contains religious and spiritual content. Furthermore, the story titled Ilyas describes the lifestyle of Muslims (Sebziyeva, 2023) and reflects Tolstoy's sympathy (Jafarov vd., 2024) and positive approach (Sebziyeva, 2023) towards Islam. It has attracted considerable interest, particularly in Muslim Eastern countries and Turkey (Мухиддинов & Хусенова, 2020). The story titled Ilyas reveals that the benefits in human life come from spirituality rather than materialism, and the religious and moral theme is deeply explored at the end of the story (Sebziyeva, 2023; Taşkın, 2021). Religious themes and the existence of God feature directly or indirectly in the story, and love for God emerges as a fundamental force that directs the individual towards goodness and compassion (Yaşar & Ceylan, 2024). Furthermore, religious motifs are seen as one of the dimensions through which happiness is attained in the story. This is because Ilyas and his wife attribute their happiness in the later parts of the story to being able to devote time to worship and spirituality for God and having ample time to pray. Regarding their finding happiness, God says, 'Now God has shown us the truth,' and the mullah present states that what is said is in the holy book (Maylıba, 2016). According to Ayday (2023), Tolstoy, in his story titled Ilyas, powerfully expresses that a person pursuing truth cannot achieve this goal amidst the anxiety of gaining and losing worldly possessions. He argues that attaining true happiness and discovering truth is possible only when a person accepts God's sovereignty and lives knowing that everything in the world belongs to Him (Ayday, 2023). Thus, the book assigns a spiritual meaning to the attainment of true happiness. Happiness seems to be possible more through spiritual elements than material things. Satisfying relationships that a person establishes with themselves, their loved ones, and the sacred, as well as a regular and balanced life, are fundamental to happiness. Therefore, including individuals' spiritual aspects in their pursuit of happiness or their interpretation of happiness is particularly important and valuable for individuals who define themselves spiritually. Indeed, studies show that religion and spirituality can contribute to happiness (Amiruddin vd., 2021; Aydin, 2019; Beyaz & Kaldık, 2018; Holder vd., 2010, 2016; Kurnaz & Şentürk, 2023; Yeter, 2019; Yorulmaz, 2016...). For this reason, the story titled Ilyas holds value for the fields of religious education, religious psychology, and spiritual counselling.

Ultimately, material resources are important for people to be able to continue their lives with security and comfort and to be happy. This is because if material resources do not meet basic needs, many situations can arise that may lead to unhappiness. However, seeking happiness solely in materialistic pursuits and working with the sole aim of becoming wealthy, without using the resources obtained for others or for good causes, can lead to unhappiness. Therefore, a balanced life is essential; people must be able to maintain a balance between themselves, their work, their family, their environment and their spirituality. Excessive material focus can negatively affect happiness by reducing the time and attention devoted to other areas. Therefore, constantly searching for happiness in material things does not guarantee happiness. Spiritual and human values beyond material things are more important for happiness. When material resources are a means to spiritual and human values, they are more meaningful for happiness. Therefore, such issues may arise during counseling processes. Clients may draw connections between their own happiness orientations and the pursuit of happiness and experiences depicted in the story. In this context, the perspectives, thoughts, statements, and preferences expressed by clients can influence the shaping of the counseling process; furthermore, they can contribute to how the client perceives and defines happiness and determine their orientation in this regard.

Based on the findings of this research, some recommendations can be made. The story "Ilyas" stands out as a bibliotherapy resource or material that can be used in spiritual-psychological counseling and guidance. Because it contains the story of a family, it can be used in couple and family counseling and family education programs. Furthermore, the story can be used in applied experimental research and training in the fields of religious psychology, psychological and spiritual counseling, and guidance. Other stories by Tolstoy that highlight the risks of acquiring wealth ("Master and Servant" and "How Much Land Needed for a Man") could also be examined.

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